

Abstract

Efficacy of Acupuncture in Alzheimer's Disease.

Eliane Pacheco Engler^{1*} and Jorge Magalhães Rodrigues¹

¹ IPTC – Research Department in Complementary Therapies, Portuguese Institute of Taiji and Qigong, Maia, Porto, Portugal.

* Correspondence: annepp21@gmail.com

Abstract

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a debilitating neurodegenerative disorder with limited therapeutic options. This narrative review explores acupuncture, a traditional Chinese medicine technique, as a promising complementary therapy for AD management.

Preclinical research indicates that acupuncture could enhance cognitive function by promoting neurogenesis and reducing neuroinflammation. Human studies also show some evidence of acupuncture's benefits in improving cognitive function. Furthermore, acupuncture may help manage common AD-related comorbidities such as depression, anxiety, and pain.

While preliminary evidence suggests acupuncture's potential, the current body of high-quality clinical trials is limited. To definitively establish its efficacy, optimise treatment protocols, and fully understand its mechanisms of action, larger, well-designed randomised controlled trials are essential. Acupuncture holds promise as a valuable complementary therapy that could significantly improve the quality of life for individuals with AD.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Alzheimer's Disease; Dementia; Neurodegenerative Diseases.

Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 2nd International Congress on Complementary Therapies in Health, held on 28 June 2025. The full-text article was published as Engler E.P., Rodrigues J.M. Exploring the Efficacy of Acupuncture in Alzheimer's Disease: A Narrative Review. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2024;2(2) [10.5281/zenodo.13308733](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13308733).

Citation: Engler E.P., Rodrigues J.M. Efficacy of Acupuncture in Alzheimer's Disease. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2025;3(2) 10.5281/zenodo.16812081

Received: 18 February 2025

Accepted: 27 February 2025

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral concerning jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).